

RAZUMEVANJE RAVNOTEŽJA MED POKLICNIM IN ZASEBNIM ŽIVLJENJEM S POMOČJO DEMATEL METODE

Razširjen povzetek:

Namen: Sodobna filozofija dela se odmika od rigidnega ločevanja dela in zasebnega življenja ter se usmerja k bolj fleksibilnemu modelu, ki poudarja usklajevanje obeh sfer. Stisnjeni delovni tedni, prilagodljiv delovni čas, pogosti odmori in možnost za aktivnosti v prostem času so postali pogosti pojav po pandemiji. Družbeni mediji so prepoznali potrebo po povezanosti dela in zasebnega življenja, saj ljudem omogočajo uspešno delovanje na obeh področjih. Kljub temu akademska literatura na tem področju še zaostaja. Ta prispevek poudarja pomen usklajevanja poklicnega in zasebnega življenja ter predstavi strukturo meril, ki so pomembna za oceno te sposobnosti.

Cilj: Glavni cilj te študije je opredeliti in raziskati ključna merila, ki vplivajo na posameznikovo sposobnost usklajevanja poklicnega in zasebnega življenja. Prav tako želi poudariti vlogo sodobnih in futurističnih praks HRM pri ohranjanju te sposobnosti in ustvarjanju kulture, ki prispeva k večjemu dobremu.

Metodologija: Študija temeljito raziskuje sodobno področje usklajevanja poklicnega in zasebnega življenja skozi literaturo in trende v družbenih medijih. Upošteva mnenja strokovnjakov iz industrije z izkušnjami na vodstvenih položajih, ki so usmerjali pri opredelitvi glavnih meril, ki vplivajo na to sposobnost. Nadaljnja analiza uporablja metodo DEMATEL za odločanje z več merili. Ta metoda je enostavna za uporabo in omogoča prepoznavanje ter razvrščanje ključnih meril za izboljšanje vodstvenih praks in uspešnosti, zlasti na neraziskanih ali premalo raziskanih področjih.

Ugotovitve: Študija identificira ključna merila za sposobnost usklajevanja poklicnega in zasebnega življenja. Prikazuje medsebojne odnose in soodvisnost teh meril ter jih prednostno razvršča na podlagi njihovega vpliva na to sposobnost. Opredeljena merila so pomembna za ohranjanje te sposobnosti.

Praktična vrednost: Študija ima veliko praktično vrednost za kadrovske in organizacijske strokovnjake ter vodje, saj jih spodbuja k razumevanju potrebe po ohranjanju usklajenosti poklicnega in zasebnega življenja zaposlenih. Rezultati študije lahko nedvomno vplivajo na izboljšave pri usklajevanju kadrovske strategije s poslovnimi cilji.

Omejitve raziskave: Študija se omejuje na prepoznavanje in raziskovanje ključnih meril usklajenosti poklicnega in zasebnega življenja. Prihodnje študije lahko razvijejo teoretične in empirične modele relevantnih dejavnikov ter preučijo vpliv posameznega dejavnika na to sposobnost. Prav tako se lahko izvede sektorsko raziskovanje te teme.

Izvirnost: Cilj te študije je raziskati in opredeliti različna merila, ki vplivajo na razvoj sposobnosti usklajevanja poklicnega in zasebnega življenja, ter predlaga verjetno izboljšanje kadrovske prakse. Ta študija predstavlja izviren prispevek vseh avtorjev. Avtorji ne navajajo navzkrižja interesov.

Ključne besede: Usklajevanje poklicnega in zasebnega življenja, Ravnovesje-prilagojenost, DEMATEL, Spreminjajoče se trende na področju upravljanja s človeškimi viri.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12657496

UNDERSTANDING WORK-LIFE FIT THROUGH DEMATEL APPROACH

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Expanded summary:

Purpose: Modern philosophy only works with flexibility. The dramatic shift from conventional practices of balancing two strict divisions, i.e. work and life, to a fused version of work-life fit is in vogue. Compressed workweeks, flexible hours, frequent breaks, and excursion activities have all emerged significantly after the pandemic. Social media has identified the need for the connection of work and life, which allows people to thrive in both aspects, but the academic literature still lags. This paper aims to highlight the need for work-life fit by presenting a structure of criteria significant in determining the work-life fit.

Objective: The main aim of this study is to identify and explore the significant criteria that determine an individual's work-life fit. It also aims to highlight the contribution of contemporary and futuristic HRM practices in maintaining this fit and creating a culture for the greater good.

Methodology: This study extensively explores the contemporary area of work-life fit through literature and social media trends. It is based on the opinions of industry experts who excel in the managerial domain which guides the identification of major criteria influencing work-life fit. The further analysis uses the DEMATEL approach in multi-criteria decision-making. This method is easy to use and can identify and prioritize sufficient criteria to improve managerial practices and performance, especially in unexplored/underexplored areas of research.

Research findings: This study aims to find significant work-life fit criteria. It shows the interrelations and interdependence of varied criteria influencing work-life fit. With the identification of criteria, it also prioritizes them based on the significant value generation of each criterion essential for maintaining a work-life fit.

Practical value: This study generates value for HR and OD practitioners and managerial experts impelling them to understand the need to maintain a work-life fit to embrace employees' transmuting needs. The current study can undoubtedly impact and suggest rigorous enhancements in aligning HR strategies with business goals.

Research limitations: This study limits its scope to mere identification and exploration of prominent criteria of work-life fit. Future studies can provide theoretical and empirical models of proper factors showing the impact of each on work-life fit. Sectoral exploration of work-life fit can also be executed.

Originality: This study aims to explore and identify varied criteria influencing the development of work-life fit and suggests probable augmentation of HR practices.

The current study is the original contribution of all the authors. We declare no conflict of interest.

Keywords: Work-life fit, Balance-to-fit, DEMATEL, Changing HR trends.

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Introduction

In the world of today workplaces are dynamic and evolving and so are the employee's expectations from their jobs. It is furthermore significant in the post-pandemic era, where a lot of existing concepts were practiced and popularised depending upon the changing needs of the organization and its people. Both HR professionals and employees have aspired to establish a balance between office and personal life, however, with evolving time alone the concept of work-life fit also came into the picture. Work-life fit is the integration of the work and personal lives together in such a way that it allows employees to manage both. Work-life fit is different from work-life balance in a way that balance could mean employees have to put equal time or effort into their work and personal lives, which could be tough. (Michigan State University, 2021)

A better fit of work and personal lives can bring employee's a lot of benefits such as less stress and increased productivity. An improved work-life fit can also increase the morale of the employees, which may help with the attraction and retention of employees as well as reduce employees' absenteeism (Canadian Centre for Occupational Health and Safety, 2016). Donny Shimamoto, the founder and managing director of an IT audit and consultancy firm based in Honolulu, has been believed to coined the term "Work-Life Fitness" in his words "It comes down to the suitability or appropriateness of the ratio of 'work' to 'life' that a person chooses to undertake at a given point in time,". (American Institute of Certified Public Accountants, 2024).

The objective of this study is to explore and observe the different aspects and criteria regarding the work-life fit. To examine the impact of alternative work arrangements such as compressed workweeks, flexible hours on employee satisfaction. Also to assess HR manager's role in facilitating communication and collaboration in remote work settings. Observing the exceptions and opinions of the employee regarding work-life fitness in their workplaces especially after the COVID-19 pandemic, which played a crucial role in redefining it. DEMATEL approach has been used in this study to analyze the collected from the working professional employed in different fields.

Need for Study

The work-life fit concept evolved around in the early twenty century and has been gaining popularity more and more in today's time. The employees have attempted to strike a perfect balance between office and personal life, which we famously known as the concept of work-life balance. However, in the post-pandemic world, we are forced to ask ourselves the question: does that magical balance exist? In the post-COVID world, this is even more relevant as we have witnessed that the traditional boundaries between work and personal life have blurred significantly, prompting a fundamental reevaluation of the way we perceive and approach work. The pandemic not only has brought in light the vulnerabilities and imbalances inherent in our professional lives but has also accelerated pre-existing trends toward alternative work arrangements and lifestyles.

As evidenced by the phenomenon of the "Great Resignation," millions of workers globally have voluntarily left their jobs in search of greater fulfillment, flexibility, and autonomy. At this point won't be wrong to say that the employee-employer relations are evolving and so is the aspiration of the employee regarding a fulfilling job. Which is bound to have an impact on job satisfaction, perceived organisational support, and overall performance. This is where work-life fit could play a significant role, while balancing could be between two opposing forces work and life, the fit is a cordial integration of work and personal life. Managing both as per the need of the situation is empowering to the employee on a both personal and professional level.

Literature review

Work-life fit, which emerged further from the concept of work-life balance, has become a crucial approach in modern workplaces, affecting both organisations and employees. It could be defined as the degree to which an individual's work requirements are also compatible with his/her family as well as personal life needs (Allen et al. 2014).

Coexisting of this combination is important since it affects organisational outcomes along with the personnel well-being of the employee. Research has demonstrated a substantial relationship between work-life fit and job satisfaction (Byron, 2005) workers report higher job satisfaction levels when they believe there is a better balance between work and personal life. On the other hand long working hours frequently result in work-life conflict, when people find it difficult to balance professional obligations with personal commitments. (Hill et al. 2001). These conflicts can have a negative impact on an employee's physical and mental health, leading to a rise in stress and a decline in general well-being. (Greenhaus and Beutell 1985).

Prioritising work-life fit is helpful for organisations in numerous ways. Organisations that provide flexible work arrangements, like telecommuting and flexible schedules, often observe reduced employee turnover rates along with higher levels of engagement (Kossek and Ozeki 1998). At the same time another important study (Darcy, McCarthy, Hill, and Grady 2012) points out that looking at work-life balance from the standpoint of a career stage can yield insightful findings from a theoretical and practical standpoint.

Businesses go beyond one-size-fits-all strategy and instead take a more customised approach to work-life balance initiatives and programs. Organisations can devise innovative strategies to tackle the challenges and intricacies of contemporary life for their workforce and start focusing on particular demographics with customised work-life balance programs. Work-life balance may take on a variety of new dimensions in the future, relying upon the development of the political, social, and economic structures (Khallash and Kruse, 2012).

This is where work-life fit can come into the picture as a more nuanced and modern approach over work life balance. An ideal work-life fit especially in today's context of the post COVID world could be an answer for better management of work as well as personal life. That would help on various other parameters to deal with the negative impact and towards a healthy and sustaining work culture. Exploring more existing literature does show the importance of flexible work arrangements, work-life balance across different fields, these are mainly in context of work life balance, however there is scope for more study on the concept of work-life fit as an emerging trend in the modern-day workplaces.

Methodology

The concept of work-life fit is highly contemporary in nature, as the need of a proper situational fit has increased with the emergence of modern workplaces. Hence, to gain better insights of the developing issue, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 11 working professionals, belonging to various fields of work. This helped us gain a 360-degree view of the concurrent issue and eliminate any probable sampling bias. This interview data is further used in content analysis aiming to identify probable fixes or influencing factors determining work-life fit.

The Decision-making Trial and Evaluation Laboratory method, invented in 1972 is used to resolve the issue of decision-making criteria in the work-life fit context. DEMATEL is the most useful in providing understanding of contemporary issues in decision-making (Tzeng et.al, 2007). It helps in finding networks, analysis importance, and arrange criteria based on cause-and-effect relations. The independence can be analysed through DEMATEL approach, which makes this method stand out of the traditional crowd of MCDM approaches (Wu, 2008).

This study is based on a multi-method, multi-sampling technique using content analysis of qualitative in-depth interviews and further DEMATEL analysis on expert-based opinions, providing a modern-day picture of work transition from balance to fit. We have incorporated the following steps given by Shieh et. al (2010):

Step 1: Each expert responded on the importance of pairwise criteria, on an integer score of 0, 1, 2, and 3. This showed the categorical influence of zero, low, medium, and high levels. The notation X_{ij} shows the influence of i on j . For $i=j$, the matrix score was set to zero, in all diagonal elements. The non-negative $n \times n$ matrix is established as $X^k = [x_{ij}^k]$, where k values from $1 \leq k \leq H$, n is the number of factors. For incorporating all the H respondents, average of all scores is constructed as follows:

$$A_{ij} = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{k=1}^H x_{ij}^k$$

Step 2: Calculating the normalised initial direct matrix. This makes all values of the matrix fall between zero to one.

Step 3: Calculating the total relation matrix. This will further lead to generation of relationship between criteria matrix, showing $c+r$ and $c-r$ matrix, highlighting the relation and prominence of each criterion. Here, the sum depicts the importance of each criterion. On the other hand, the difference depicts the effect of one criterion on the other.

Step 4: The final matrix is calculated based on a threshold value to obtain a digraph. The effects greater than the threshold value, match and meet the digraph.

The overall DEMATEL framework is executed using the R software, with a Dematel package installed in it.

Results

The idea of DEMATEL is based on content analysis of semi-structured interviews conducted with 11 industry professionals from various fields. This ensured our study to maintain the rigor and collect first hand perspectives of working professionals within numerous areas of operation. Proceeding further, we inculcated the shortlisted criteria through content analysis of the interview responses to identify prominently influencing factors in creating and maintaining the work-life fit.

According to the content analysis, the criteria identified ranged from flexible arrangements to leadership, as explained in the *Fig 1*.

- Setting Boundaries
- Optimizing Wellbeing
- Alignment of Commitments
- Balance of Aspirations
- Balance of Efforts
- Demographics
- Social Norms
- Nature of Job
- Organisational Support
- Leadership

Figure 1: Chart of criteria

The potent of the above criteria was then assigned scores based on the choices of industry experts from fields like banking, operations, information technology, and education. The scores ranged from 0 to 3, following the steps provided by Shieh et. al (2010).

Further, for executing the DEMATEL analysis, the first step of averaging is executed for pairwise selection scores of 10 industry experts, shown as follows:

Table 1: X¹

Factors	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
A. Flexible Arrangements	0	3	3	3	2	3	0	0	1	3	0
B. Setting Boundaries	2	0	3	3	2	3	1	0	0	0	2
C. Optimizing Wellbeing	3	3	0	3	3	2	3	2	2	2	2
D. Alignment of Commitments	2	3	3	0	1	3	1	2	1	2	2
E. Balance of Aspirations	2	3	3	3	0	3	3	3	3	0	0
F. Balance of Effort	0	3	3	2	2	0	1	0	0	1	2
G. Demographics	3	3	3	2	2	3	0	2	3	1	2
H. Social Norms	3	3	3	2	1	3	0	0	3	0	1
I. Nature of Job	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	0	3	2
J. Organizational Support	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	0	3	0	3
K. Leadership	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	0	2	3	0

Table 2: X²

Factors	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
A. Flexible Arrangements	0	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	0	1	2
B. Setting Boundaries	1	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	2	1
C. Optimizing Wellbeing	1	1	0	2	1	0	2	1	0	2	0
D. Alignment of Commitments	3	2	2	0	1	3	2	2	1	2	2
E. Balance of Aspirations	3	3	2	2	0	2	1	2	2	0	0
F. Balance of Effort	3	3	2	3	3	0	2	1	3	1	2
G. Demographics	0	1	1	0	2	0	0	1	2	0	0
H. Social Norms	0	1	2	3	3	2	2	0	2	2	2
I. Nature of Job	2	2	2	3	3	3	2	2	0	2	3
J. Organizational Support	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	3	3	0	3
K. Leadership	3	2	3	3	2	3	3	1	1	3	0

Table 3: X³

Factors	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
A. Flexible Arrangements	0	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
B. Setting Boundaries	0	0	2	2	1	3	1	0	1	1	1
C. Optimizing Wellbeing	0	3	0	3	0	3	0	0	1	1	0
D. Alignment of Commitments	0	2	3	0	1	3	0	0	1	2	2
E. Balance of Aspirations	0	2	2	2	0	2	0	0	2	0	0
F. Balance of Effort	0	3	3	3	2	0	1	1	2	2	1
G. Demographics	0	3	3	3	2	3	0	2	1	0	0
H. Social Norms	2	2	1	2	2	3	1	0	1	0	0
I. Nature of Job	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	0	0	2	2
J. Organizational Support	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	0	3
K. Leadership	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	0

Table 4: X⁴

Factors	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
A. Flexible Arrangements	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
B. Setting Boundaries	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	0
C. Optimizing Wellbeing	0	1	0	1	0	2	0	1	0	0	0
D. Alignment of Commitments	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
E. Balance of Aspirations	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
F. Balance of Effort	0	2	2	2	0	0	0	2	2	0	2
G. Demographics	3	3	3	3	3	3	0	3	3	3	3
H. Social Norms	0	3	3	3	3	3	0	0	2	2	0
I. Nature of Job	3	2	2	1	0	0	2	2	0	1	1
J. Organizational Support	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	0	3
K. Leadership	3	3	3	3	3	0	1	3	3	3	0

Table 5: X⁵

Factors	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
A. Flexible Arrangements	0	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
B. Setting Boundaries	2	0	2	3	3	2	2	0	3	0	0
C. Optimizing Wellbeing	2	3	0	3	3	2	2	0	3	0	0
D. Alignment of Commitments	2	2	2	0	3	1	1	1	2	0	0
E. Balance of Aspirations	3	3	3	3	0	3	3	3	3	3	3
F. Balance of Effort	3	3	3	3	3	0	3	3	3	3	3
G. Demographics	0	2	2	3	3	2	0	2	2	0	0
H. Social Norms	0	0	0	0	2	1	2	0	2	0	0
I. Nature of Job	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	0	1	2
J. Organizational Support	3	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	0	2
K. Leadership	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	0

Table 6: X⁶

Factors	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
A. Flexible Arrangements	0	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
B. Setting Boundaries	0	0	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0
C. Optimizing Wellbeing	3	3	0	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
D. Alignment of Commitments	0	1	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
E. Balance of Aspirations	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
F. Balance of Effort	3	3	3	3	3	0	3	3	3	3	3
G. Demographics	0	1	1	2	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
H. Social Norms	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0
I. Nature of Job	2	2	2	3	1	3	2	2	0	2	2
J. Organizational Support	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	0	3
K. Leadership	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	0

Table 7: X⁷

Factors	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
A. Flexible Arrangements	0	0	0	0	2	2	2	0	0	0	0
B. Setting Boundaries	1	0	2	2	2	3	3	3	0	1	1
C. Optimizing Wellbeing	3	3	0	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
D. Alignment of Commitments	0	0	1	0	1	2	2	2	0	1	0
E. Balance of Aspirations	3	3	3	3	0	3	3	3	3	3	3
F. Balance of Effort	0	1	1	2	0	0	1	2	0	0	0
G. Demographics	3	1	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
H. Social Norms	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	0	3	3	3
I. Nature of Job	0	0	1	1	0	2	1	1	0	0	0
J. Organizational Support	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	0	3
K. Leadership	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	0

Table 8: X⁸

Factors	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
A. Flexible Arrangements	0	3	3	2	2	2	2	0	3	3	3
B. Setting Boundaries	2	0	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	3	2
C. Optimizing Wellbeing	2	2	0	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	2
D. Alignment of Commitments	2	0	1	0	3	2	1	1	2	2	2
E. Balance of Aspirations	2	1	2	3	0	3	2	1	2	2	2
F. Balance of Effort	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	2	2	2
G. Demographics	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	2	1	2	2
H. Social Norms	0	2	2	1	0	0	2	0	1	1	2
I. Nature of Job	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	2	2
J. Organizational Support	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	1	2	0	3
K. Leadership	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	3	0

Table 9: X⁹

Factors	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
A. Flexible Arrangements	0	3	3	2	3	3	1	3	2	2	0
B. Setting Boundaries	3	0	3	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	3
C. Optimizing Wellbeing	3	2	0	2	3	2	1	2	1	2	3
D. Alignment of Commitments	3	2	2	0	2	3	2	2	3	2	1
E. Balance of Aspirations	3	3	2	2	0	3	2	1	2	3	3
F. Balance of Effort	3	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	2	2
G. Demographics	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	2
H. Social Norms	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	0	1	2	3
I. Nature of Job	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	1
J. Organizational Support	3	2	2	3	3	2	2	1	2	0	1
K. Leadership	1	2	2	3	3	2	1	3	1	1	0

Table 10: X¹⁰

Factors	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
A. Flexible Arrangements	0	1	3	2	3	3	1	3	2	2	0
B. Setting Boundaries	3	0	1	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	3
C. Optimizing Wellbeing	3	1	0	1	3	2	3	2	1	3	3
D. Alignment of Commitments	3	2	2	0	2	3	2	2	3	2	1
E. Balance of Aspirations	3	3	2	2	0	3	2	1	3	1	3
F. Balance of Effort	3	2	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	2	2
G. Demographics	1	2	2	2	1	2	0	2	2	3	2
H. Social Norms	0	2	2	1	1	1	2	0	1	2	3
I. Nature of Job	3	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	0	2	1
J. Organizational Support	3	2	2	3	3	2	2	1	2	0	0
K. Leadership	0	2	2	3	3	2	1	3	1	1	0

The average of all the choice scores is calculated as follows:

Table 11: Initial average

Factors	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
A. Flexible Arrangements	0	2.33	2.33	2.00	2.33	2.44	1.78	1.56	1.67	2.00	1.56
B. Setting Boundaries	1.22	0	1.78	1.78	1.78	2.22	1.22	0.78	1.00	1.00	1.11
C. Optimizing Wellbeing	1.89	2.33	0	2.33	2.00	2.11	1.67	1.44	1.67	1.67	1.44
D. Alignment of Commitments	1.33	1.44	1.78	0	1.33	2.22	1.00	1.11	1.11	1.22	1.00
E. Balance of Aspirations	1.78	2.00	1.89	2.00	0	2.22	1.67	1.44	2.00	1.22	1.22
F. Balance of Effort	1.56	2.44	2.33	2.44	1.89	0	1.44	1.44	1.89	1.56	1.89
G. Demographics	1.22	1.78	2.00	1.78	1.67	1.67	0	1.78	1.67	0.89	1.00
H. Social Norms	1.00	1.78	1.78	1.67	1.67	1.78	1.56	0	1.89	1.11	1.22
I. Nature of Job	2.33	2.22	2.11	2.22	1.67	2.11	2.00	1.56	0	1.67	1.67
J. Organizational Support	3.00	2.78	2.78	2.67	2.78	2.33	2.44	2.11	2.67	0	2.67
K. Leadership	2.78	2.78	2.78	2.89	2.67	2.44	2.44	2.22	2.33	2.78	0

Table 12: Normalised relation

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11
C1	0	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.05
C2	0.04	0	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.08	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.04
C3	0.07	0.08	0	0.08	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.05
C4	0.05	0.05	0.06	0	0.05	0.08	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03
C5	0.06	0.07	0.07	0.07	0	0.08	0.06	0.05	0.07	0.04	0.04
C6	0.05	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.07	0	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.05	0.07
C7	0.04	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.06	0	0.06	0.06	0.03	0.03
C8	0.03	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.05	0	0.07	0.04	0.04
C9	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.07	0.05	0	0.06	0.06
C10	0.11	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.08	0.09	0.08	0.01	0	0.1
C11	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.11	0.1	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.1	0

Table 13: Total relation

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11
C1	0.16	0.27	0.27	0.26	0.25	0.27	0.21	0.19	0.21	0.2	0.18
C2	0.15	0.13	0.19	0.2	0.18	0.21	0.15	0.12	0.14	0.13	0.13
C3	0.21	0.26	0.17	0.26	0.23	0.25	0.2	0.17	0.2	0.18	0.17
C4	0.16	0.18	0.19	0.14	0.17	0.21	0.14	0.13	0.15	0.14	0.13
C5	0.2	0.23	0.23	0.24	0.15	0.24	0.19	0.17	0.2	0.16	0.16
C6	0.2	0.26	0.26	0.27	0.23	0.18	0.19	0.18	0.21	0.18	0.19
C7	0.16	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.19	0.2	0.11	0.16	0.18	0.13	0.13
C8	0.16	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.19	0.21	0.17	0.1	0.18	0.14	0.14
C9	0.23	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.23	0.26	0.21	0.19	0.15	0.19	0.19
C10	0.31	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.32	0.33	0.28	0.25	0.29	0.17	0.26
C11	0.3	0.34	0.34	0.35	0.31	0.33	0.28	0.25	0.28	0.27	0.17

Table 14, depicts the direct/indirect relation between all the choices determining work-life fit. The final threshold value is calculated as 0.214.

According to Table 14, the importance of all criteria can be comprehended as

C10>C11>C6>C3>C1>C9>C5>C4>C2>C7>C8

(based on the c+r prominence analysis)

Here, organizational support and leadership are prime factors defining work-life fit, while the social norms and demographics hold low importance in this context.

Complementary to the importance, organizational support, leadership, flexible arrangements, and nature of job are the factors directly and strongly influencing other factors of work-life fit. The most affected outcome variables are setting boundaries and alignment of commitment for an individual, based on the (c-r) values.

Table 14: Relation-Prominence Matrix

	ci	ri	c+r	c-r
C1	2.53	2.28	4.81	0.25
C2	1.78	2.75	4.53	-0.97
C3	2.34	2.71	5.05	-0.37
C4	1.78	2.77	4.55	-0.99
C5	2.2	2.49	4.69	-0.29
C6	2.39	2.73	5.12	-0.34
C7	1.94	2.17	4.11	-0.23
C8	1.96	1.95	3.91	0.01
C9	2.47	2.25	4.72	0.22
C10	3.27	1.93	5.2	1.34
C11	3.26	1.89	5.15	1.37

The digraph, represented in Fig 2, shows clear effects on alignment of commitment and setting boundaries by mostly all other variables in the dataset. The least prominent and least affecting/ influenced variables turned out to be social norms and demographics. This suggests that societal influence is still not the defining criteria for an individual to decide the path of a perfect fit, whereas the family structure and phase of life till defines a part of work-life fit.

The dual relations happen to connect C11 & C10, C3 & C6, C5 & C3, C5 & C6, C9 & C1, C1 & C3, C9 & C6. This is an indication of understanding the two-way effect of these variables, associated together as a pair, and defining work-life fit. For example, organisational support and leadership are collaborated, affecting each other, and shaping the organizational environment. This certainly is a major part of an individual work aspect, which is further associated with the life aspect to maintain a proper fit. Here, leaders have the potential to define the comfort one feels while working in an organization. This is complemented by the existing support throughout in the organization.

Figure 2: Criteria Digraph

Findings

Based on the DEMATEL analysis, this study supports the that the superlative focus of managers lies in four following causes:

- i. Increased flexibility (C1)
- ii. Nature of job (C9)
- iii. Organisational support (C10)
- iv. Leadership (C11)

This is mainly to cater the needs of changing workforce in the modern era, where premium organisational environment is the staple need of work. The managers need to prioritise their emphasis from working of setting boundaries (C2) and alignment of commitment (C4) to the impending issues of optimisation of well-being (C3), balance of employee aspirations (C5), and balance of effort (C6).

This can be achieved by identifying the upskilling opportunities for employees and supportive HR policies like education funding, child care leaves, menstrual sickness support, job-person fit rotation, old age care support, and other leadership development training programmes. Understanding employees need for job and personal ambitions should be a management concern, to achieve organisational loyalty in the long run. Profit motives or mechanistic approach are highly precluded by the new generation-wide workforce. The high worth and significance of organisational support and leadership clearly indicates the proactiveness of managers at all levels to create a positive work aura.

The managers can identify loopholes within their organization through the lens of this study and plan for training that can be imparted to increase communication of goals. For individuals, this study helps in identifying the need of work-life fit in both growth and survival mode. HR managers should primarily focus on understanding the organizational environment in terms of leadership. They can then be well-equipped to guide the employees to growth, proficiency, and creativity. Modern managers are bound to understand the personal elements of employees to better shape the work environment and increase psychological loyalty within

the organization. This study addresses that gap of unaddressed importance of work-life fit, with a multi-method multi-sampling technique to present a clear picture of the modern-day need, work-life fit.

Conclusion

The current study has incorporated two approaches to address the problem of work-life fit: qualitative content analysis and DEMATEL framework. It is based on the dual opinions of working professionals and industry experts on the issue of work-life fit. Through the content analysis, 11 important criteria are found, which are then used to execute the DEMATEL technique, aimed at understanding the multi-criteria-based decision-making in shaping the work-life fit. The participants of this study belonged to various fields of operation, showing a pervasive need for work-life fit and common influential aspects of the same.

DEMATEL technique is used to highlight the pairwise associations and its importance in the problem context. This method critically analyses the prominence and relations of factors influencing work-life fit. The results show that organizational support and leadership are the major prominent causes, and setting boundaries and aligning commitment are major challenges within the arena of work-life fit. Other mediating aspects ranged from the nature of the job to the balance of efforts and aspirations, predefining the need for work-life fit. This study highlights the role of HR managers in the workplace, who need to clasp the dual aspect of the work-life balance and redefine it to an integrated individual fit.

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